

Think Fast! Learning to Control Online Reasoning in Stochastic Environments

Supplementary Material

A EXPERIMENT DOMAIN DESIGN

ObstacleRacetrack. ObstacleRacetrack MDPs are generated by sampling a graph from a high-level graph structure in a grid of 5×3 nodes. The close goal line must be within 2 cells of the initial position, and the shortest path to the far goal line must be 10 cells from the initial position. Loops are possible in the high-level graph. The high-level graph is upscaled to a 2D grid of cells, with each graph node being represented by a 7×7 grid of cells. 7×7 cell grids are randomly generated to match the connectivity of the corresponding graph node. Obstacle states (which act as wall cells or empty cells depending on whether the obstacle is present) are placed to block the path between the initial position and close goal. This forms the x and y state factor space of the sampled MDP. The maximum velocity is 3 in any direction, so $v_x \in \{-3, -2, \dots, 2, 3\}$ and $v_y \in \{-3, -2, \dots, 2, 3\}$. Colliding with a wall or obstacle sets x and y velocities to 0, and the agent transitions to the closest cell to the wall or obstacle in the direction of its velocity vector before the collision. The action failure probability for the MDP is sampled $p_{\text{fail}} \sim \mathcal{U}(0.0, 0.2)$. The probability of the obstacle being present is sampled $p_{\text{obstacle}} \sim \mathcal{U}(0.5, 0.8)$. Both of these probabilities are provided as context features to the metalevel controller. As the obstacle state factor is $e \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$, the maximum number of states in ObstacleRacetrack MDPs is 108045 ($7[v_x] \times 7[v_y] \times 3[\text{obstacle}] \times 35[x] \times 21[y]$). As wall states are unreachable, the number of reachable states is smaller. Nine examples of ObstacleRacetrack environments from the evaluation set are shown in Figure 8.

In ObstacleRacetrack, the duration τ of one `PLAN` action in the object-level algorithm is 12500 Bellman updates. The maximum budget of Bellman updates is 400K, so the maximum number of `PLAN` actions the agent can take in one episode is 32.

For *OffLearn*, the default object-level policy in this domain is to accelerate to a velocity of 1 along the centre of the track to the far away goal. Introducing obstacle-adaptive behaviour into the default policy would make the default policy overly well-performing compared to other metalevel algorithms without access to a default policy.

For this domain, the object-level algorithm is provided with uninformative initial value function values, set to 0 for all states for the lower bound value function, and 100 for the upper bound value function.

RadWorld. RadWorld problems are generated with a multi-step process. First, physical obstacles are placed in a 60×50 grid. The maximum number of obstacles is 10, and the maximum total number of obstacle cells is 15% of the grid. Obstacles are variations of rectangles and L-shapes with randomly sampled orientations, side lengths and thicknesses. The obstacle grid undergoes a binary dilation with a 3×3 kernel to blend nearby obstacles together, followed by applying random binary noise. This is finally followed by a binary erosion with a 3×3 kernel to remove small holes and small obstacles. The initial and goal positions are randomly sampled from a truncated Gaussian distribution with mean $(5, 5)$ and $(55, 45)$

respectively, and a standard deviation of 2. Problem instances are discarded where obstacle placement makes the goal unreachable.

The radiation level distribution in the environment is generated by simulation of radiation sources with $\frac{1}{r^2}$ radiation decay with distance. The joint distribution of radiation source numbers, strengths and locations is designed to generate few large radiation sources and increasingly large numbers of small radiation sources. Noise is added to the radiation level distribution to represent random variation due to environment construction and shadowing effects. For 30% of the cells in the environment, the radiation level is multiplied by $0.5 + 0.5 \cdot \text{Gamma}(1.2, 1.2)$. In order not to unfairly bias results against the offline metalevel controller and to reduce variance between evaluation runs, the radiation level at the initial state is set to the median radiation level across the environment. Nine examples of RadWorld environments from the evaluation set are shown in Figure 9.

In RadWorld, the duration τ of one `PLAN` action in the object-level algorithm is 5000 Bellman updates. The maximum budget of Bellman updates is 320K, so the maximum number of `PLAN` actions the agent can take in one episode is 64.

For *OffLearn*, the default object-level policy in this domain was to take actions that led to states with the lowest 8-connected total distance to goal (taking into account obstacles), with ties broken via the smallest Euclidean distance to goal. This results in a default policy that takes the shortest available diagonal path to the goal while avoiding obstacles.

For this domain, the object-level algorithm was provided with initial value function values based on a scaled 8-connected distance to goal (taking into account obstacles). This distance measure was multiplied by the maximum possible radiation level for the upper bound value function and by the minimum possible radiation level for the lower bound value function, to give admissible initial value function values. We also tested uninformative initial value function values as in the previous domain, but this leads to high variance in how long BRTDP takes to find a goal state to terminate the first trial. This can lead to metalevel controller performance being heavily biased by how quickly the object-level algorithm finds a goal state in the first trial, which is not representative of the performance of the metalevel controller.

B ADDITIONAL RESULTS

B.1 Varying Cost of Planning

We carried out an additional round of training and evaluation in the ObstacleRacetrack domain, doubling the value of τ to 25K Bellman updates and the maximum planning time budget to 800K Bellman updates. This is equivalent to halving the cost of planning in the environment. The results are shown on the right-hand side of Figure 4, where the left-hand side shows the results from the main text for comparison. The same trends in cost performance are observed, with *OnLearn* significantly outperforming the baselines. General performance is improved across the board due to the decreased cost of planning, but the relative performance between methods is similar. The *DTP* methods still perform best with the plan/act ratio

(a) Normalised cost-to-goal for the method and baselines, reproduced from Figure 2a in the main text.

(b) Normalised cost-to-goal for the method and baselines, when the cost of planning is halved.

(c) Planning time distribution for the method and baselines, reproduced from Figure 2b in the main text.

(d) Planning time distribution for the method and baselines, when the cost of planning is halved.

Figure 4: Cost performance and planning time distributions in the ObstacleRacetrack domain, when planning is made cheaper by a factor of 2.

set to 0.2, but the difference between parameterisations is more pronounced at this lower cost of planning. In terms of planning time (Figures 4c and 4d), both online methods tended to use fewer planning steps for the blocked path case, and a similar number of planning steps for the no obstacle case.

We carried out an additional round of training and evaluation in the RadWorld domain, doubling the value of τ to 10K Bellman updates. The maximum planning time budget was left unchanged, so the maximum number of `PLAN` actions the agent can take in one episode is 32. This makes planning faster, scaling radiation cost per Bellman update down by a factor of 2. The results are shown on the right-hand side of Figure 5, where the left-hand side shows the results from the main text for comparison. Compared to the full planning cost case, the mean excess cost decreases by 41% for *OnLearn*, 50% for *OffLearn*, and 40% for *Bounds*. In this setting, *OffLearn* outperforms *Bounds* significantly. The best parameterisation of *DTP* is still around 0.5 compared to 0.7 previously, but there is no significant performance difference between the two parameterisations. The performance difference between parameterisations is more pronounced at this lower cost of planning. *DTP* with a plan/act ratio of 0.5 slightly outperforms *Bounds*, but the difference is not statistically significant.

B.2 Other Learning Algorithms

Results shown in previous sections used DQN [23] as the learning algorithm for the online metareasoner *OnLearn*. In this section

we evaluate two alternative learning algorithms: PPO [27] and A2C [22]. For the two policy gradient methods, we used the default hyperparameters from Stable Baselines3 [25], other than changes to better match the distributional nature of the problem setting. For PPO, the batch size and number of steps for each environment per update were set to 512. For A2C, the number of steps for each environment per update was set to 64. These values were identified as the best-performing values using a parameter sweep. Similarly to DQN, we trained with 16 environments in parallel and used frame stacking with a stack size of 3. We also tested PPO with a recurrent policy, but found this did not outperform frame stacking.

Figure 6 compares the performance of DQN, PPO, and A2C for the online metareasoner in both the ObstacleRacetrack and RadWorld domains. In ObstacleRacetrack (Figure 6a), DQN outperforms PPO and A2C by a small margin ($\sim 10\%$), but in RadWorld (Figure 6b) it incurs slightly higher cost. PPO and A2C perform similarly across both domains, with PPO slightly outperforming A2C in ObstacleRacetrack. In both domains, PPO and A2C perform statistically significantly better than the baselines, similarly to DQN.

The replay buffer and TD updates used by DQN allow it to learn more efficiently in our setting, where the object-level problem distribution induces a meta-RL problem, compared to the on-policy methods. The two on-policy methods required more than twice as much training to reach comparable performance, and were more sensitive to hyperparameter settings than DQN.

(a) Normalised cost-to-goal for the method and baselines, reproduced from Figure 3a in the main text.

(b) Normalised cost-to-goal for the method and baselines, when the cost of planning is halved.

Figure 5: Cost performance and planning time distributions in the RadWorld domain, when planning is made cheaper by a factor of 2.

(a) Normalised cost-to-goal for the online metareasoner with different learning algorithms in the ObstacleRacetrack domain.

(b) Normalised cost-to-goal for the online metareasoner with different learning algorithms in the RadWorld domain.

Figure 6: Comparing the performance of using different deep reinforcement learning algorithms for the online metareasoner.

B.3 Domains from Budd et al. [8]

We evaluated the method and baselines on the two domains from Budd et al. [8], DeepSeaTreasure and Racetrack. The results are shown in Figure 7. Values reported for *OffLearn* differ from those in Budd et al. [8] because we fix the cost of planning for *OffLearn* to be the cost of the NOP action in the initial state, whereas in Budd et al. [8] the cost of planning was drawn from a distribution.

In the DeepSeaTreasure domain, we observe a large gap between mean and median cost performance for most algorithms. This arises from a long tail of particularly high-cost episodes, caused by a poor initial policy and the stochastic nature of the environment. *Bounds* performs especially poorly in terms of mean performance in this domain, as it frequently myopically decides not to improve its initial low-quality policy. The performance of *DTP* is highly sensitive to the plan/act ratio in this domain, resulting in widely varying mean cost performance.

B.4 Additional Object-Level State Observations for RadWorld

We also ran RadWorld experiments with an agent-centric observation window around the current state, giving a field of view of 9×9

cells. This resulted in a 10% (statistically significant) decrease in performance, which did not decrease with additional training time.

B.5 Out-of-Distribution Problem Instances

We evaluated ObstacleRacetrack with obstacle presence probability $\mathcal{U}(0.2, 0.5)$ rather than the training distribution $\mathcal{U}(0.5, 0.8)$:

Algorithm	Mean	Median	Std Dev
<i>OnLearn</i>	1.863	1.792	0.563
<i>OffLearn</i>	2.069	2.030	0.620
<i>Bounds</i>	1.786	1.617	0.514
Best <i>DTP</i> , 0.3	1.869	1.692	0.549

Table 1: Normalised cost-to-goal for the method and baselines on out-of-distribution ObstacleRacetrack problem instances with obstacle presence probability $\mathcal{U}(0.2, 0.5)$.

The RL-based methods show expected performance degradation on out-of-distribution problems, while the non-learning methods

(a) Normalised cost-to-goal for the method and baselines in the DeepSeaTreasure domain [8].

(b) Normalised cost-to-goal for the method and baselines in the Race-track domain [8].

Figure 7: Cost performance results for the domains from Budd et al. [8].

maintain performance. This validates that *OnLearn* has learned problem distribution-specific behaviour, rather than simply memorising fixed heuristics.

C IMPLEMENTATION

The metalevel MDP is implemented using the Gymnasium interface [31]. *Bounds* and *DTP* algorithms use a smaller action set consisting only of `PLAN` and `ACT` actions, rather than the full hyperparameter setting action space.

DTP variants aim to choose between `PLAN`/`ACT` actions to keep the ratio of planning to acting as close as possible to their target. They are limited by the same total planning time budget, meaning that higher planning ratios may exceed the budget during the episode and only `ACT` thereafter. The same total planning budget applied to *Bounds*, but this algorithm did not tend to use the full budget. Also, *DTP* agents must `PLAN` when they have no action specified by their object-level policy, so they may `PLAN` for more than one timestep in the initial state to generate an initial valid policy.

RL algorithm implementations were from Stable Baselines3 [25], version 2.3.2. DQN parameters are set to their default values, except for increasing the number of gradient steps per rollout to match the number of environment steps taken in that rollout. The size of the hidden layer was 64, and the number of hidden layers was 2.

We enforced a maximum planning time budget, both to ensure that training episodes terminate and because there is no benefit to planning longer than the convergence point of the object-level algorithm’s solution. As the DQN implementation used does not support action masking, we force the `ACT` action to be selected if the maximum planning time budget is reached. We also implemented truncation at a maximum number of environment interactions, to stop episodes in the case where the agent `ACTS` on a poor policy and spreads its planning time budget over many object-level states, leading to it not generating a valid goal-reaching policy within the maximum planning time budget. We did not observe this occurring in practice for the domains tested.

C.1 Object-level Planner: WBRTDP

WBRTDP was implemented in single-threaded C++. The WBRTDP algorithm is described in Budd et al. [8]. (W)BRTDP trials have varying lengths when they terminate only on reaching a goal state. This means that the end of a metalevel timestep τ likely does not coincide with the end of a BRTDP trial. Although idealised as an anytime algorithm, the state of the object-level algorithm is not consistent in the middle of a trial if interrupted. Rather than implementing functionality to break trials and restore the state of the object-level algorithm as it was before the trial if the number of Bellman updates exceeds that allowed for the metalevel timestep, we instead use checkpointing of the object-level algorithm state to return a copy of the state at the start of the trial. When future planning actions are taken, the state at the end of the trial can be returned if it was reached within the new allowed number of Bellman updates.

We use similar algorithm features as in Budd et al. [8]. As we are using a deep learning-based agent, we can provide many algorithm features to the learning agent, and it should learn which are useful. However, we do not want to calculate complex observation features because this adds metareasoning overhead. The features provided are the upper and lower Q-value bounds at the current state, the total number of trials completed so far, the number of states visited during all trials, the number of states visited during the last trial, and the number of trials that have passed through the current state.

When updating the planner with the new state s' , as described by the transition function $T_{\mathcal{M}}^{\chi, s}(\chi' | \chi, s')$, the planner is set to run from a state sampled from the transition function $T_{\mathcal{M}}(s', \text{NOP}, \cdot)$, *not* from the current state. This is because after committing to planning, the earliest that plan can be executed is after the `NOP` action is completed, one object-level timestep later.

C.2 Evaluation

During evaluation, stochastic outcomes in the object-level MDP are seeded based on the evaluation MDP ID. The ground-truth values of epistemic state factors, such as the presence of the obstacle in `ObstacleRaceTrack`, are sampled when the MDP is created. During evaluation, outcomes of stochastic actions which depend on

Figure 8: Example ObstacleRacetrack environments from the evaluation set.

epistemic state factors are rejection sampled to match the ground-truth epistemic state factor values. Evaluation is carried out with deterministic metalevel action selection for learning-based policies.

Each RL agent is evaluated on the same 1000 held-out evaluation problem instances, giving 5000 total evaluation runs per RL agent. Baseline methods (*Bounds*, *DTP*) are deterministic, so we evaluate them once per test problem (1000 runs). Because we seed environment stochasticity identically per problem instance, rerunning baselines multiple times would yield identical results.

C.3 Compute Hardware

Training was carried out with 16 training environments trained in parallel on a machine with an AMD Ryzen Threadripper 7960X

CPU (24 cores, base clock 4.2 GHz) and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4090 GPU. Training was CPU-bound due to CPU-based object-level planning dominating the time taken to simulate episode steps. With this parallel training configuration, training one agent on the ObstacleRacetrack domain took approximately 12 hours, and training one agent on the RadWorld domain took approximately 3 hours. The number of training steps was $\sim 10^6$ for both of these domains.

This compute hardware was also used for evaluation, and for preliminary experiments (not reported in this work) to validate the system implementation and analyse performance.

Figure 9: Example RadWorld environments from the evaluation set.